

A Novel Spray Reagent for Flavones and Quinones

M. MASOOD, ASHOK PANDEY and K. P. TIWARI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

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THE present investigation was carried out to find some new spray reagent for detecting the presence of flavones and quinones.

Experimental

The paper chromatograms were developed with butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5 v/v) and sprayed with 1% aqueous solution of borax. The spray reagent does not give colour reaction with completely methylated flavone and 3-hydroxy 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxy flavone. The colour intensity has been found to increase in the case of compounds containing vicinal hydroxyl groups.

This reagent has been found to be equal in performance on comparison with the known spray reagents¹⁻⁵ viz. *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, 25% aqueous lead acetate (basic), 5% aqueous sodium carbonate, methanolic sulphuric acid and 1% methanolic sodium hydroxide solution.

The R_f values and the colour with the spray reagent are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Name of compounds	R_f	Colour observed with the reagent
2-hydroxy 1 : 4 naphthaquinone	0.84	Br
1,8-dihydroxy 3-methyl anthraquinone	0.76	Br
1,8,8-trihydroxy 3-methyl anthraquinone	0.64	LP
1,8-dihydroxy 3-methyl 6-methoxy-anthraquinone	0.94	LP
1,6-dimethoxy 8-hydroxy 3-methyl-anthraquinone	0.11	V
7-hydroxy flavone	0.00	LY
5,7-dihydroxy flavone	0.67	LY
5,7-dihydroxy flavone	0.57	LY
5,7-dihydroxy 4'-methoxy flavone	0.50	Y
5-hydroxy 3',4'-dimethoxy flavone	0.43	LY
5-hydroxy 7,3',4'-trimethoxy flavone	0.38	Y
5,3'-dihydroxy 7,4'-dimethoxy flavone	0.52	Y
3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol	0.85	Y
3,5,3',4'-tetrahydroxy 7-methoxy flavonol	0.80	Y
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavonol	0.78	Y
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavanone	0.84	LBr
3',5,7-trihydroxy flavone	0.91	Y
5,7,4'-trihydroxy 3,6,3'-trimethoxy flavonol	0.61	LY
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavonol	0.86	LBr
3,5,7,3',4'-pentamethoxy flavonol	0.70	—
3-hydroxy 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxy flavonol	0.88	—
3,5,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavanone-7-O-galactoside	0.73	Br
5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol-3-O-rhamnoside	0.82	Y
5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol-3-O-rutinoside	0.56	Y

Br=brown, LP=light pink, V=violet, LY=light yellow, Y=yellow, LBr=light brown.

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Ionisation Constants of Some New Substituted Pyridyl Thioureas

O. P. KHURANA, A. D. TANEJA* and J. S. TYAGI**

Department of Chemistry, D. N. College, Hissar, Haryana

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THERE is a general paucity of information regarding acid base equilibria of substituted pyridyl thioureas except for the work of Prasad¹ and Kashyap² who studied the ionisation constants of some substituted pyridyl thioureas. So it was thought desirable to determine the ionisation constants of some N'-2-(substituted-pyridyl)-N-substituted-thioureas and to know the effect of substituents on the thermodynamic ionisation constants of these compounds.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present studies were of BDH AnalaR quality. The compounds N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-phenylthiourea, (HPPTuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolylthiourea, (HPPT-TuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolylthiourea, (HPOTTuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-ethylthiourea, (HPETuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-phenyl-thiourea, (4MPPTuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolyl-thiourea, (4MPPT-TuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolyl-thiourea, (4MPOTTuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-ethyl-thiourea, (4MPE-TuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-phenyl-thiourea, (6MPPTuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolyl-thiourea, (6MPPT-TuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolyl-thiourea, (6MPOTTuH) and N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-ethyl-thiourea, (6MPETuH) were prepared as described earlier³.

These compounds were purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The purity of all these compounds was checked by melting points. The pK_a

* Asst. Biochemist, HAU, Hissar, Haryana.

** Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut, U. P.